

Characteristics and nature of Citizen Science in Europe today

Citizen Science in Europe, as elsewhere, continues to manifest itself in a variety of different ways. While attracting interest across multiple sectors of society, its definition remains unclear. The first CS Track **White Paper on Themes, objectives and participants of citizen science activities** has just been published and along with the initial results of the first large scale survey into participation in Citizen Science, provides an important snapshot of the nature of citizen science in Europe.

The CS Track project is broadening our knowledge about Citizen Science by investigating Citizen Science activities, disseminating good practices and formulating knowledge-based policy recommendations.

CITIZEN SCIENCE PROJECT THEMES

We've found that the main CS project themes tend to be from agricultural, biological and environmental sciences while emerging themes include applied sciences like engineering, medicine, and government policy-related fields.

Along with the emergence of a variety of different themes, we also noted that how Citizen Science projects are set up and managed is changing in different ways.

THE CHANGING NATURE OF CITIZEN SCIENCE PROJECTS

• An increasing number of projects are hosted virtually, have online components and/or have implemented technology as part of the project...

- Digital technology and social media has increased the attention Citizen Science projects receive as well as participation.
- Citizen Science is particularly helpful in supporting research fields where the large scale collection of data is vital but where resources are limited.
- Citizen scientists' work can be a crucial link in the production of scientific knowledge, which may be used to influence research-based policy decisions.

- The availability of smartphones and related technologies has helped to diversify Citizen Science away from traditional areas such as birdwatching and astronomy.
- Citizen Science is playing an increasing role in applied sciences like engineering, medicine, and government policy-related fields.

64% of respondents took part in citizen science projects that belong to biology and ecology research areas.

Around 1 in 10 citizen scientists are helping develop physics and astronomy research projects.

- Citizen scientists are also reporting small, everyday things that support and uphold crucial public infrastructure, such as mapping potholes.
- Solving mega-challenges like climate change requires multidisciplinary research, this increasingly multidisciplinary aspect is also evident in Citizen Science projects.

- Taking part in Citizen Science can also work as a low-barrier introduction to various fields of science that might otherwise be out of reach or difficult to approach.
- Doing Citizen Science in your own chosen field contributes to lifelong learning, which can have a benefit in terms of social inclusion, and active citizenship..

RE-ASSESSING THE VALUE OF CITIZEN SCIENCE PROJECTS

- Scientists are able to conduct time-consuming and expensive projects that cannot be done without the support of citizen scientists.
- Citizen Scientists can get a better understanding of scientific processes which is helpful at times when trust in scientific processes is low like during a pandemic.
- Participation in Citizen Science projects can help those taking part further develop their skills and competences and have an impact on society and political decision-making.

This Briefing Report is based on the CS Track Public Deliverable 4.2 entitled White paper: Themes, objectives and participants of citizen science activities, download the full deliverable [here](#).

Additional statistical evidence comes from the first analysis of the results of the large-scale survey into Citizen Science project participation carried out by CS Track in early 2021, complete results to be published later in 2021.

Download the full report available [here](#).

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